

**PREDICTIVE FACTORS FOR THE OUTCOME OF NON-
INVASIVE VENTILATION IN PEDIATRIC ACUTE
RESPIRATORY FAILURE**

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Complete List of Authors:	Muñoz-Bonet, Juan Ignacio; Hospital Clínico Universitario, Unidad Cuidados Intesivos Pediátricos Flor-Macián, Eva María; Hospital Clínico Universitario, Unidad Cuidados Intesivos Pediátricos Brines, Juan; Hospital Clínico Universitario, Servicio Pediatría Roselló-Millet, Patricia; Hospital Clínico Universitario, Unidad Cuidados Intesivos Pediátricos Llópis, María Cruz; Hospital Clínico Universitario, Servicio Pediatría López-Prats, José Luis; Hospital Clínico Universitario, Unidad Cuidados Intesivos Pediátricos Castillo, Silvia; Hospital Clínico Universitario, Unidad Cuidados Intesivos Pediátricos
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8 **PREDICTIVE FACTORS FOR THE OUTCOME OF NON-INVASIVE VENTILATION IN**
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10 **PEDIATRIC ACUTE RESPIRATORY FAILURE**
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14 Juan Ignacio Muñoz-Bonet, MD; Eva M Flor-Macián, MD; Juan Brines, PhD *; Patricia
15 M Roselló-Millet, MD; M Cruz Llopis, MD *; José L López-Prats, MD; Silvia Castillo,
16 MD.
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22
23 Pediatric Intensive Care Unit; (*) Pediatric Service. Hospital Clínico Universitario.
24 Valencia (Spain)
25
26

27
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30 Reprints will be ordered.
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32
33
34 Address for reprints: Dr. Juan I. Muñoz Bonet.
35 UCIP Hospital Clínico Universitario.
36 Avda. Vicente Blasco Ibáñez 17.
37
38
39
40
41 46010 Valencia, Spain.
42
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44
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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Non-invasive ventilation (NIV) constitutes an alternative in the treatment of pediatric Acute Respiratory Failure (ARF). However it shouldn't delay endotracheal intubation (ETI) when it's necessary. The aim of this study is to identify success and failure prognostic signs of NIV in pediatric ARF.

Design: Prospective non-controlled clinical study.

Setting: Pediatric intensive care unit (PICU) in a university hospital.

Patients: Children (1 month -16 years) with moderate to severe ARF who received NIV through the use of an Evita 2 Dura fitted with an NIV module (Dräger), during a four year period. Failure was defined by the need for ETI.

Measurements and results: Nine out of 47 cases (19.1%) needed ETI between the 3rd and 87th hour after the start of treatment (33.6 ± 29.6 hours). Failure was associated with the youngest age group (4 ± 3.3 vs 7.7 ± 5 years, $p < 0.04$), ARDS (failure/ARDS: 5/10 vs failure/non ARDS: 4/37, $p=0.013$) and worsening radiographic images taken at 24 and/or 48-72h ($p=0.001$ and $p<0.001$ respectively). A significant reduction in heart rate was observed between the 2nd and 4th hours after the start of NIV (130 ± 25.8 vs 116 ± 27.7 beats per minute, $p<0,001$) and pCO_2 (54.1 ± 19.5 vs 48.6 ± 14.3 torr, $p<0.007$) only in the success group. Breathing assistance was higher in the failure group, both initial and maximum assistance. In the multi-variant analysis only maximum mean airway pressure and FiO_2 formed part of the discriminant success/failure function with a cut-off point of 11.5 cmH₂O and 0.57 respectively.

Conclusions: Modifications in the patient's respiratory assistance will be made depending on their clinical, gasometrical and radiological evolution. Mean airway pressure and FiO_2 values higher than 11.5 cmH₂O and 0.6 respectively, predicts failure and possibly set the limits above which the risks of delaying intubation increase.

INTRODUCTION

Acute Respiratory Failure (ARF) is one of the main reasons of admission to an Intensive Care Unit (ICU). The endotracheal intubation (ETI) and conventional mechanical ventilation (CMV) are frequently necessary in the treatment of these patients. To reduce complications associated with these techniques, other breathing support techniques have been developed such as non-invasive ventilation (NIV). Numerous controlled studies and meta-analysis have shown its efficiency in different adult forms of ARF (1, 2, 3), but in pediatrics, ARF experience is limited showing favourable results in patients with Post-Extubation ARF (4), heightening Chronic Respiratory Failure (CRF) (5) and Hypoxemic ARF (6, 7). Although NIV has been more and more accepted in the treatment of different types of pediatric ARF, there is little information available about the limits of its application. At the moment this is the main inconvenience for its use. Although the aim of NIV is to gain control of ARF avoiding intubation, when this is needed, its application shouldn't be delayed in order to avoid a worse prognosis. This is the main reason to look for reliable failure signs of the technique. In adults, several retrospective (8, 9) and prospective (10, 11) studies have identified some factors which can predict the success of NIV. Information of this kind is lesser in children (12, 13). The aim of this study is to identify prognostic signs related to the application of NIV in pediatric ARF, in order to allow us to carry out an adequate use of the technique and detect early on which patients need ETI and CMV.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We performed a prospective non-controlled clinical study on children admitted to the PICU who were treated by use of NIV, over a period of 4 years. The unit is a multi-valent PICU which has 6 beds in a tertiary University Hospital. The study was approved by the Institutional Review Board, and informed parental written consent was obtained. We carried out NIV on ARF pediatric patients, aged between 1 month and 16 years,

when the opinion of the pediatric critical care physician was that the patient could require ETI. Patients fitted the following clinical or gasometrical criteria:

1. Respiratory rate (RR) increased for their age (14) and moderate to severe signs of respiratory distress, reading more than 4 on the Clinical Score chart used (Table 1), and/or
2. Hypoxemic ARF (type 1): $\text{PaO}_2 < 60$ torr or $\text{Sat O}_2 < 90\%$ with $\text{FiO}_2 > 0,5$ (15) and/or
3. Hypercapnic ARF or mixed (type 2): $\text{pH} < 7.35$ with $\text{PaCO}_2 > 50$ torr (15, 16).

Post-extubation ARF was defined as the appearance of clinical ARF with the above criteria, in the immediate post-extubation period. For the diagnosis of Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS) and pneumonia both the criteria adopted by the American-European Consensus (17) and CDC (18), were used respectively. Newborns were excluded, along with those with a need for immediate intubation or incapacity to protect the air way, hemodynamic instability in spite of blood volume expansion (> 60 mL/Kg) and the use of vasoactive drugs (except Dopamine < 10 mcg/Kg/min), malformations and traumatism, facial burns, no drain pneumothorax, severe digestive haemorrhage, serious obstruction of the superior airway, abundant respiratory secretions and absolute absence of collaboration (19-23).

A volumetric ventilator with a specifically fitted NIV module was used (Evita 2 Dura, Dräger Medical, Lübeck, Germany) with active humidification in all cases (Fisher and Paykel Healthcare, Auckland, New Zealand). The starting ventilator mode was used as continuous positive airway pressure with pressure support (CPAP+PS) in post-extubation ARF and in Type I moderate, and bi-level positive airway pressure with pressure support (BIPAP+PS) in the rest of the cases. This mode was also employed on patients where CPAP+PS was initially used but the patient's evolution was not favourable. As an interface, we used mouth-nasal masks (non-vented): Mirage model

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4 (Resmed, Poway, CA), Performatrack (Respironics, Murrysville, PA) or Hans Rudolph
5 masks (Hans Rudolph Inc, Kansas City, Missouri). Clorazepatic dipotassium (0.5-1
6 mg/kg/day) or Midazolam (0.05-0.1 mg/kg/hour) was administered to all patients to
7 improve mask tolerance and adaptation to mechanical ventilation (MV), according to
8 medical criteria. A decompressive nasogastric tube was used according the attending
9 pediatric physician criteria. All patients were kept on an absolute diet until the need for
10 intubation was ruled out. Oral feed was started when the patient's situation allowed the
11 provisional withdrawal of NIV.
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22 The criteria to establish failure of the treatment were: withdrawal due to major
23 complications, technical poor tolerance and/or inability to stabilize the progression of
24 respiratory failure needing ETI (24).
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29 The following variables were analysed to determine the success/failure prognostic
30 signs:
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33 1. Nominal and ordinal variables:

- 34 - Sex.
- 35 - Underlying disease.
- 36 - Cause and type of ARF.
- 37 - Need for sedation.
- 38 - Method of initial MV used (CPAP + PS vs. BIPAP + PS).
- 39 - Hemodynamic support: defined by the need for vasoactive drugs higher to
40 Dopamine 5 mcg/kg/min. and/or blood volume expansion more than 20
41 mL/kg in the first 24 hours.
- 42 - Appearance of complications brought on by the use of NIV.
- 43 - Respiratory evolution accomplished between (0, 2 and 6 hours) using the
44 Clinical Score chart (Table 1).
- 45 - Thorax X-ray given at the beginning and after 24 and 48-72 hours. The
46 evaluation was performed by a pediatric radiologist who had no previous
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4 knowledge of the patient's clinical evolution. Patients with a normal X-ray at
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6 the beginning were excluded.

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8 2. Scale variables (quantitatives):
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11 - Age.
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13 - Respiratory assistance (initial and maximum): peak inspiratory pressure
14 (PIP), positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP), pressure support (PS),
15 mean airway pressure (MAP) and FiO₂. Oxygen was administered by a
16 Venturi mask, reservoir mask or nasal prongs before the starting of NIV.
17 When nasal prongs were used, FiO₂ was calculated by using the formula:
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$$\text{FiO}_2 = 20 + 4 \times \text{oxygen flow in L/min (25)}$$

20 The later FiO₂ value was
21 measured by MV.
22
23 - NIV application time and length of PICU stay.
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25 - RR, heart rate (HR) and blood pressure (BP) measured (0 and 2-4 hours).
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27 - pH and blood gases (0 and 2-4 hours): capillary samples were taken in most
28 of the patients (arterialized blood by heating the peripheral extremity), being
29 the attending pediatric physician who determined the need to obtain arterial
30 samples.
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32 - Arterial oxygen saturation (SatO₂) by pulxiosimetry through the use of
33 Masimo technology ® (Radical, Datascope, Irvine, CA) at 0 and 2-4 hours.
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35 - PELOD mortality score during the first 24 hours.
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48 *Statistical analysis:* The SPSS statistic package 14.0 for Windows was used to
49 analyze statistics. ANOVAs were used for continuous variables between subjects and
50 T tests for related values. Repeated measured designs were also used (intra-subject).
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52 In the case of multiple comparisons, Type I errors were corrected using the Bonferroni
53 adjustment. For the assessment of prognostic signs in the case of ordinal variables,
54 Wilcoxon matched-pairs ranks test for related values was applied and the Kruskal-
55 Wallis test for comparisons within groups. The exact Fisher test was used for
56 dichotomic variables and the Ji-square for 2x3 tables. For the scale variables a
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discriminant analysis was used along with an analysis of the ROC curve. A p value of 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

During the study period 208 patients were admitted with ARF. Of these 98 (47.1%) required positive pressure respiratory assistance: 51 cases (52.1%) were treated with CMV. In the remaining 47 (47.9%) we applied NIV. This group included 37 patients, 25 boys and 12 girls aged between 1 month and 16 years (average age 7.1 ± 4.9 years). Of these patients 12 suffered psychomotor delay and 10 immunosuppression (IS). The most frequent causes of ARF were pneumonia in 20 cases (42.5%), followed by ARF post-extubation in 11 (23.4%) and ARDS in 10 (21.3%). The type of respiratory failure was mixed, or hypercapnic in 25 cases (53.2%) and hypoxemic in 14 (29.8%). In 8 patients (17%) the criteria used for applying NIV was exclusively clinical.

In 9 patients (19.1%) NIV failed due to the progression of ARF, requiring ETI and CMV. NIV failure was observed between hours 3 and 87 (average 33.6 ± 29.6 hours). Two patients were given intubation between 3 and 12 hours, 4 between 12 and 48 hours and 3 after 48 hours. The causes for failure were: serious ARDS ($\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$ post-intubation 101.5 ± 50.6 mmHg) in 5 patients (55.5%) associated with IS in 3 cases (33.3%), pneumonia associated with severe broncho-obstructive crisis in 2 cases (22.2%) and post-extubation ARF in another 2 (22.2%).

No relationship was found between the success/failure evolution and sex, underlying disease and the type of respiratory failure. The age of the failure group was significantly less (4 ± 3.3 vs. 7.7 ± 5 years, $p < 0.04$) and it was linked to the diagnosis of ARDS (ETI/ARDS: 5/10 vs. ETI/no ARDS: 4/37, $p = 0.013$). Although it didn't reach significant level, the PELOD score tended to be higher in the failure group (20.3 ± 35.2 vs. 5.6 ± 14.2 , $p = 0.052$).

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4 No patient needed to have treatment stopped due to lack of tolerance. Cloraceptic
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6 Dipotasic was administered to 20 patients and conscious sedation with Midazolam to
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8 27. The use of sedation wasn't linked in any way to the result. Hemodynamic
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10 assistance was necessary in 16 patients and again it wasn't related to the result.
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13 NIV produced a significant improvement both clinically and statistically on the
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15 clinical score, between 0 and 2 hours (6 ± 2.1 vs. 3.9 ± 1.7 , $p < 0.001$) as well as between
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17 2 and 6 hours (3.9 ± 1.7 vs. 2.9 ± 1.6 , $p < 0.001$). However neither the initial scores nor
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19 subsequent evolution were related to the result.
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22 Significant initial improvement was observed also in RR, HR, pH, $p\text{CO}_2$ and SatO_2
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24 (Table 2). However, only HR and $p\text{CO}_2$ evolution were related to the result (Table 3).
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27 On the initial X-ray, one quadrant was involved in 6 patients (12.8%), 2 quadrants
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29 in 24 (51%), 3 quadrants in 3 (6.4%) and 4 quadrants in 7 (14.9%). No significant
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31 alterations existed in 7 cases (14.9%), 6 because of post-extubation ARF and 1
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33 because of bronchiolitis. The level of initial X-ray involvement wasn't related to the
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35 result.
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38 An improvement was observed at 24 hours ($n=39$) in 26 cases (66.6%), worse
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40 progress in 3 (7.6%) and there was no change in 10 cases (25.6%). Between 48 and
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42 72 hours ($n=37$) improvement was noted in 26 patients (70.2%) ##(Figure 1)##, worse
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44 progress in 5 patients (13.5%) and no change was seen in 6 patients (16.2%).
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47 Worsening of X-ray images at 24 hours and/or between 48 and 72 hours was
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49 associated significantly to NIV failure ($p= 0.001$ and $p < 0.001$, respectively), all patients
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51 requiring ETI and CMV.
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54 Complications were minor and linked to the use of the interface, although in none of
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56 the cases was it necessary to withdraw NIV. The most frequent complication was minor
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58 erosion and irritant dermatitis on the bridge of the nose (29.8%). Three patients had
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60 signs of irritative conjunctivitis (6.4%). No relationship was found to exist between
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62 complications and the outcome.
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65 In 14 cases, initially CPAP+PS was used being successful in 7. The other 7 needed
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4 psychomotor delay (7) and IS (13, 29) since the application of NIV could benefit them
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6 especially (7, 29, 13).
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8 In agreement with our results and those of other authors (12, 26) the risk of failure is
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10 higher in patients of younger age, therefore extra vigilance should be practised. With
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12 this purpose scores to note seriousness could also be useful at the time of admittance,
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14 as it seems to indicate in our results and has been observed by other authors (13).
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17 As in other pediatric studies (7, 12, 24, 26) pneumonia has been the most frequent
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19 cause of ARF, followed by ARF post-extubation (12, 13, 26, 28, 30). Use of NIV on
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21 similar adult patients is controversial (8, 11, 31). Although there is little information, its
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23 use is also controversial in the treatment of ARDS, in adults (32, 33). In pediatrics, only
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25 Essouri et al (13) study its use in these patients, showing a failure level of 78% that in
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27 our study dropped down to 50%. In spite of this, ETI was avoided in the other 50% of
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29 cases. This fact is especially relevant with IS being 6 in these 10 patients (13, 29). For
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31 this reason, we believe that diagnosis of ARDS shouldn't contradict its use. It should be
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33 used early on, in the acute lung injury or SDRA slight ($PaO_2/FiO_2 >150$ mmHg), and
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35 under monitoring as not to delay intubation whenever necessary.
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39 Avoiding ETI delay is in our opinion the cornerstone of NIV use in ARF. That's why
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41 it's important to have objective predictive factors to determine which patients and when
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43 should be intubated. It's important because this moment, as we have seen in our study
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45 and as in others, can range from a few hours to days (13, 26, 28).
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48 Initial evolution of the clinical and gasometrical parameters has been put forward as
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50 signs of success/failure (8, 9, 11, 34). In our study, just like in the study of Bernet et al
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52 (12) the initial improvement of *RR* in both groups (success and failure) suggests that
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54 this is an initial sign of adaptation to NIV treatment and not necessarily an indication of
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56 success. The same occurs with the interpretation of the initial improvement of *pH*,
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58 *oxygen saturation* and the clinical score. Although the evolution of *HR* and *pCO₂* are
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60 related to the result, we believe its role is similar. This way the initial improvement of
these parameters would be related to the "adaptation or initial success" being able to

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4 condition subsequent progress of the illness to the failure of NIV. In our opinion, the
5 continuous valuation of these parameters is useful in order to be able to modify the
6 ventilatory assistance and whenever necessary evaluate the need for ETI.
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10 Radiological assessment seems especially interesting as a prognostic sign. This
11 way, although it's initial affectation by quadrants isn't related to the result, the
12 worsening of the X-ray image at 24 hours and then between 48-72 hours, is a clear
13 sign of the progression of the illness and is useful in predicting late failure of NIV.
14 Therefore unfavourable X-ray evolution obliges us to keep special control, having not
15 ruled out the need for ETI. We haven't found any information about the use of thorax X-
16 ray as a prognostic sign in other studies.
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25 Neither have we found studies which use the patient's respiratory assistance as a
26 predictive factor. In our study several ventilatory parameters, initial as well as at the
27 moment of maximum assistance, were linked to the result. However, only two
28 parameters made up the discriminating success/failure function. *Maximum MAP*, which
29 absorbs all the power from the effects of the other pressure parameters. So an MAP
30 higher than 11.5 cmH₂O predicts failure in nearly 90% of the cases, independent of the
31 time taken for the illness to progress. Although it is possible to see that this value
32 fluctuates slightly in other studies, we believe that it marks the limit of treatment that
33 NIV can provide. This is why we can consider the MAP a sign of failure at any moment
34 during the progress of ARF. The second parameter, *FiO₂* during the time of maximum
35 assistance, we believe has a complementary use to the previous. This way whilst
36 treating a patient with NIV, if we can't reduce FiO₂ down to a safe level ($\leq 0.5-0.6$), in
37 spite of intensifying respiratory assistance and other treatment measures, there is a
38 high risk that NIV will fail. In our study a FiO₂ higher than 0.57, during the time of
39 maximum assistance predicted failure in nearly 80% of the cases. Bernet et al (12) had
40 already observed that the evolution of the initial FiO₂ acted as a sign of early failure. In
41 our study we observed that this parameter is useful at any moment during the progress
42 of ARF. Now to be correctly interpreted it must be valued together with the MAP. These
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4 parameters allow us at any moment during the progress of ARF to evaluate its
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6 seriousness and plan for the most convenient therapeutic management.
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10 CONCLUSIONS

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12 We think that clinical, gasometrical and radiological evolution should guide the
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14 modifications in the patient's respiratory assistance. The value of the MAP and the FiO_2
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16 together allow us to evaluate the intensity of the treatment. In our study, MAP and FiO_2
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18 values higher than 11.5 cmH_2O and 0.6 respectively, predicts failure and possibly set
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20 the limits above which the risks of delaying intubation increase.
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Figure 1. Significant thorax X-ray improvement after 72 hours (right side) from the beginning of NIV (left side) in two patients with ARDS and immunosuppression who didn't need ETI.

For Peer Review

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12 Figure 2. Failure group (n=9): comparison of parameters for maximum
13 assistance used in NIV and CMV. Respiratory assistance needed by these
14 patients was significantly higher after having passed through CMV. PEEP,
15 positive end-expiratory pressure; PIP, peak inspiratory pressure; MAP, mean
16 airway pressure. (a) $p < 0.015$, (b) $p < 0.020$, (c) $p < 0.008$.
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Clinical signs	Score		
	0	1	2
Intercostal/sternal retractions	no	Costal	costal+sternal
Thoraco-abdominal dissociation	no	Moderate	High
Nasal Flaring	no	Slight	High
Expiratory groan	no	at auscultation	Yes
Cyanosis (Sat. O ₂)	no (>92%)	With air (<92%)	With FiO ₂ >0, 4 (<92%)
Conscience level	normal	depression/restlessness	lethargy/maximum restlessness
Score: <4:slight, 4-6:moderate, >6:severe			

Table 1. Clinical score: it was applied a synthesis of Silverman and Wood-Downes test, applicable to any type of pediatric ARF. We used the Silverman test, using the evolution of the costal and sternal retractions as the only parameter, and we included the evaluation of the level of consciousness and of cyanosis of the Wood-Downes score. This last parameter was evaluated by pulseoximetry, instead of PO₂ and clinical evaluation.

n = 47	Previous NIV	After NIV	p value
RR (b/m)	44 ± 15.8	33.7 ± 12	< 0.001
HR (bpm)	133.1 ± 26.1	121 ± 29.9	< 0.001
SAP (mmHg)	108.4 ± 18	109.3 ± 16.3	NS
DAP (mmHg)	58.4 ± 13.3	58.6 ± 11.8	NS
pH	7.34 ± 0.11	7.36 ± 0.07	< 0.001
pCO₂ (torr)	55.1 ± 19.2	49.8 ± 14.7	< 0.001
SatO₂ (%)	90 ± 8.8	95.4 ± 3.8	< 0.001
PaO₂ (torr) *	102.1 ± 42.6	116 ± 32.1	NS
FiO₂	0.52 ± 0.23	0.51 ± 0.17	NS

Table 2. Clinical and laboratory variables before the start of NIV and after a period of 2-4 hours of the treatment. (*) n = 12; RR, respiratory rate; b/m, breaths/minute; HR, heart rate; bpm, beats per minute; SAP, systolic arterial pressure; DAP, diastolic arterial pressure.

	Failure (n = 9)	Success (n = 38)	p value	Effect size	Strength of the test
HR before NIV (bpm)	145.9 ± 24.8	130 ± 25.8 ^a	NS		
HR after 2-4 hours (bpm)	142.2 ± 31	116 ± 27.7 ^a	< 0.02	12.2 %	68.6 %
RR before NIV (b/m)	51 ± 11.3 ^b	42.4 ± 16.3 ^a	NS		
RR after 2-4 hours (b/m)	37.1 ± 8.9 ^b	32.9 ± 12.6 ^a	NS		
pH before NIV	7.34 ± 0.09	7.34 ± 0.11 ^a	NS		
pH after 2-4 hours	7.37 ± 0.06	7.36 ± 0.07 ^a	NS		
pCO₂ before NIV (torr)	59.4 ± 18.5	54.1 ± 19.5 ^c	NS		
pCO₂ after 2-4 hours (torr)	55.2 ± 16.3	48.5 ± 14.1 ^c	< 0.04	9.6 %	55 %
SatO₂ before NIV (%)	92 ± 6 ^d	89.5 ± 9.4 ^d	NS		
SatO₂ after 2-4 hours (%)	95.1 ± 3.6 ^d	95.5 ± 3.9 ^d	NS		

Table 3. Initial progress of the success/failure groups and uni-variant analysis of the clinical and analytical parameters according to the results (success/failure) of NIV. HR, heart rate; bpm, beats per minute; RR, respiratory rate; b/m, breaths/minute. (a) $p < 0.001$; (b) $p < 0.02$; (c) $p < 0.007$; (d) $p < 0.004$.

	Initial assistance	Maximum assistance
FiO₂	0.5 ± 0.2 (range 0.21-0.9)	0.5 ± 0.2 (range 0.3-1)
PIP (cmH₂O)	17.7 ± 2.9 (range 14-23)	19 ± 2.7 (range 15-25)
PEEP (cmH₂O)	5.4 ± 1.1 (range 4-9)	6 ± 1.2 (range 4-9)
PS over PEEP (cmH₂O)	9.7 ± 2.1 (range 5-14)	10.6 ± 2.5 (range 5-18)
MAP (cmH₂O)	8.7 ± 1.7 (range 6-12)	10 ± 2.2 (range 6-15)

Table 4. Initial and maximum assistance (n = 47). PIP, peak inspiratory pressure; PEEP, positive end-expiratory pressure; PS, pressure support; MAP, mean airway pressure.

	NIV Failure	NIV Success	p value	Effect Size	Strength of the test
Initial breathing assistance					
PEEP (cmH₂O)	6.2 ± 1.5	5.2 ± 0.9	< 0.015	19.7 %	89.6 %
PIP (cmH₂O)	19.4 ± 2.9	17.2 ± 2.7	= 0.07		
PS (cmH₂O)	10.8 ± 1.1	9.5 ± 2.2	= 0.06		
MAP (cmH₂O)	9.8 ± 1.9	8.5 ± 1.6	< 0.04	13.3 %	73.8 %
FiO₂	0.59 ± 0.15	0.52 ± 0.18	NS		
Maximum assistance					
PEEP (cmH₂O)	6.9 ± 1.2	5.8 ± 1.1	< 0.02	17.3 %	85 %
PIP (cmH₂O)	20.5 ± 2.1	18.5 ± 2.7	= 0.053		
PS (cmH₂O)	12 ± 1.5	10.2 ± 2.5	< 0.005	8.3 %	50.8 %
MAP (cmH₂O)	12.5 ± 1.2	9.4 ± 2	< 0.001	32 %	99.4 %
FiO₂	0.64 ± 0.13	0.45 ± 0.17	< 0.005	17.3 %	85 %

Table 5: Respiratory assistance according to NIV result. PEEP, positive end-expiratory pressure; PIP, peak inspiratory pressure; PS, pressure support; MAP, mean airway pressure.

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